

Angelo Leogrande¹

Cash Flow of European Banks

Between Q3-2014 and Q4-2021 it increased by 408%

The European Banking Authority-EBA calculates the value of cash flows as part of the composition of assets or *Asset Composition-Cash Balances*". The data is therefore expressed as a percentage of bank assets.

Ranking of European countries by value of cash flow in the fourth quarter of 2021. Lithuania ranks first by value of cash flow in the fourth quarter of 2021 with an amount of 0.42, followed by Cyprus with a value of 0.39357, and from Latvia with a value of 0.36339. In the middle of the table are Germany with an amount of 0.1593, followed by Portugal with an amount of 0.15562, and Italy with an amount of 0.1513. Denmark with an amount equal to 0.06868, Poland with an amount equal to 0.02941, and the Czech Republic with an amount of 0.02293 close the ranking.

Ranking of European countries by percentage change in the value of cash flow between Q3-2014 and Q4-2021. Holland ranks first in terms of the percentage change in cash flows between Q3-2014 and Q4-2021 or equal to a value of 2205.85% equal to an amount of 0.14 units, followed by Italy with a variation of 1536.66% equal to an amount of 0.14 units and Ireland with a variation equal to 753.65% equal to an amount of 0.26 units. In the middle of the table there are Denmark with a value equal to 334.55% equal to 0.05 units, followed by Cyprus equal to 326.66% equal to 0.30 units and Slovakia with a value equal to 290.49% equal to 0.11 units. Romania closes the ranking with a value equal to 2.21% equal to 0.0029 units, followed by Poland with a value equal to -27.99% equal to an amount of -0.01 units and by the Czech Republic with a value equal to -63.04% equal to an amount of 0.04 units. On average for the countries indicated, the value of cash flows as a component of assets improved by 408.36% or 0.13 units.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm: Silhouette coefficient vs. Elbow method. A clustering with k-Mean algorithm optimized by means of the Silhouette coefficient is carried out below. The analysis shows the presence of two clusters, namely:

- *Cluster 1:* Spain, France, Portugal, Netherland, Greece, Italy, Slovakia, Hungary, Denmark, Serbia, Finland, Belgium, Austria, Poland, Iceland, Germany, Czech Republic, Ireland, Croatia, Slovenia, Romania, Luxembourg, Malta;
- *Cluster 2:* Latvia, Estonia, Lithuania, Cyprus, Bulgaria.

Considering the value of the medians of the individual clusters, it follows that the value of the median of the cash flows of the countries of cluster 1 is equal to 0.149, while the value of the median of the cash flows of the countries of cluster 2 is equal to 0.363 units. Therefore, the following ordering of the clusters derives, namely: $C2 = 0.36339 > C1 = 0.149183$. From the point of view of clustering it appears that the Baltic countries - added to Malta and Bulgaria, have a cash flow value almost 2.43 times higher than the other European countries.

¹ Ph.D., Assistant Professor at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, European Union. Email: leogrande.cultore@lum.it

However, if you decide to optimize the k-Means algorithm not using the Silhouette method, but rather the Elbow method, about 4 clusters result. Therefore, recalculating with $k = 4$ the following aggregations result, that is:

- *Cluster 1*: Portugal, Denmark, Spain, Poland, Italy, Slovakia, Greece, Czech Republic, Iceland, Hungary, France, Netherland;
- *Cluster 2*: Latvia, Estonia, Lithuania;
- *Cluster 3*: Slovenia, Luxembourg, Croatia, Ireland, Romania, Germany, Austria, Bulgaria, Malta, Belgium, Serbia, Finland;
- *Cluster 4*: Cyprus.

By calculating the median value of the clusters, the following ordering of the clusters results: in first place there is Cluster 4-C4 with an amount equal to 0.39357, followed by Cluster 2-C2 with a value equal to 0.36339, by cluster 3 -C3 with a value of 0.19017 and from Cluster 1-C1 with a value of 0.14259. Therefore, the following ordering of the clusters derives from it, that is $C4 > C2 > C3 > C1$. Looking at the map drawn with clustering with the Elbow method, there is a greater ability to identify geographical areas by value of cash flows. Except for cluster 4-C4 which is made up of a single country or Cyprus, it is possible to identify a distinction between the Baltic countries and the area of Central-Northern Europe with medium-high values of cash flow, and Europe southern Italy which instead has the lowest cash flow values in Europe.

In this case, therefore, it is preferable to use clustering with the Elbow method as it allows to better represent the distinctions between the various countries by cash flow value.

Machine Learning and Predictions. Subsequently, predictions were made using machine learning algorithms. 80% of the data was used for training the algorithms. The algorithms were compared in terms of predictive performance or the ability to maximize R-squared and minimize MSE, RMSE, MAE. Algorithm rankings are then created for each statistical indicator and the ranking of the individual algorithms is added together. The lower the value of the sum of the ranking of the algorithms, the greater the predictive efficiency of the algorithms. Therefore, the following ordering of the algorithms in terms of predictive capacity derives from it, that is:

- *Gradient Boosting* with a payoff of 8;
- *Linear Regression* and *AdaBoost* with a payoff of 10;
- *Tree* with a payoff value of 15;
- *Random Forest* with a payoff value of 17;
- *kNN* with a payoff value of 24;
- *Neural Network* with a payoff value of around 28.

By applying the Gradient Boosting algorithm it is possible to almost perfectly predict the dynamics of the cash flow with a percentage error calculated on the average of the variations between predicted values and original values equal to 0.00002332424%.

Conclusion. The value of cash flow present in European banks controlled by the EBA-European Banking Authority increased on average by about 408% between Q3-2014 and Q4-2021. In general, the value of bank cash flow tends to grow in all countries except Poland and the Czech Republic. The clustering analysis shows that the Baltic countries, Cyprus, and the countries of Central and Northern Europe are virtuous in terms of cash flow, while the countries of Southern Europe have low levels of cash flow. To predict the trend of the variable of interest, it is possible to use the Gradient Boosting algorithm which is very efficient in terms of minimizing statistical errors and maximizing R-squared.

References

- Leogrande, Angelo, et al. "Italian Universities: Institutional Mandate and Communitarian Engagement." *European Journal of Educational Management* 2.2 (2019): 85-110.
- Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Matarrese, M. (2022). Innovative SMEs Collaborating with Others in Europe.
- Leogrande, A., Laureti, L., & Costantiello, A. (2022). The Innovation Index in Europe. Available at SSRN 4091597.
- Leogrande, A. (2022). The Export of High Knowledge Intensity Services of European Countries (No. 112795). University Library of Munich, Germany.
- Leogrande, A. (2022). Export of Medium and High-Tech Products in Europe. University Library of Munich, Germany.
- Leogrande, A. (2022). Workers in the Knowledge Economy in Europe (No. 112538). University Library of Munich, Germany.
- Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Satisfaction with the Environmental Condition in the Italian Regions between 2004 and 2020. *Journal of Environmental Protection*, 13(4), 299-314.
- Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M. M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Enterprises Providing ICT Training in Europe (No. 111756). University Library of Munich, Germany.
- Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M. M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Employment in Innovative Enterprises in Europe. University Library of Munich, Germany.
- Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., Leogrande, A., & Marco, M. (2021). The Innovation Linkages in Europe. University Library of Munich, Germany.
- Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(11), 166-187.
- Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., De Cristoforo, G., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The Innovation-Sales Growth Nexus in Europe. University Library of Munich, Germany.
- Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2021). Human Resources in Europe. Estimation, Clusterization, Machine Learning and Prediction.
- Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). Estimation and Machine Learning Prediction of Imports of Goods in European Countries in the Period 2010-2019. University Library of Munich, Germany.
- Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2021). The Impact of Venture Capital Expenditures on Innovation in Europe. University Library of Munich, Germany.
- Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, D. (2021). The Determinants of Design Applications in Europe. University Library of Munich, Germany.
- Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The Intellectual Assets in Europe. University Library of Munich, Germany.

LEOGRANDE, A., COSTANTIELLO, A., & LAURETI, L. (2021). The Broadband Penetration in Europe. *Journal of Applied Economic Sciences*, 16(3).

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2020). The Finance-Innovation Nexus in Europe. *IJSET-International Journal of Innovative Science, Engineering & Technology*, 7(12).

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The Innovation-Friendly Environment in Europe. Available at SSRN 3933553.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Angelo, L. (2021). The Corporate Innovation in Europe.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The attractiveness of European research systems. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(10), 72-101.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. The Determinants of Human Resources in European Countries During the Period 2010-2019.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The Determinants of Innovation in European Countries in the period 2010-2019. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(8), 91-126.

Clusterizzazione con algoritmo k-Means: il metodo del Coefficiente Silhouette Vs Metodo di Elbow.

In questo caso viene scelto il metodo di Elbow in quanto riesce meglio a dare una rappresentazione dei vari raggruppamenti dei paesi europei per valore del flusso di cassa.

Model	MSE	RMSE	MAE	R2
Neural Network	0.002	0.046	0.034	0.781
kNN	0.001	0.039	0.030	0.845
Linear Regression	0.000	0.008	0.006	0.993
Random Forest	0.000	0.021	0.015	0.955
Tree	0.000	0.012	0.009	0.984
AdaBoost	0.000	0.003	0.001	0.999
Gradient Boosting	0.000	0.000	0.000	1.000

Ranking dei paesi Europei pe Cash Flow

Rank	NSA	Q4-2021	Rank	NSA	Q4-2021
1	LT	0,42531	16	IT	0,151304025
2	CY	0,39357	17	FR	0,149183281
3	LV	0,36339	18	EU	0,148987309
4	IE	0,29198	19	NL	0,143898922
5	MT	0,27201	20	SK	0,143320652
6	LU	0,2641	21	ES	0,141859357
7	SI	0,23597	22	RO	0,13636029
8	EE	0,22227	23	FI	0,127222981
9	HR	0,21231	24	SE	0,11405881
10	BG	0,20042	25	HU	0,086862063
11	GR	0,19404	26	IS	0,081454795
12	AT	0,17992	27	DK	0,068682217
13	BE	0,1781	28	PL	0,029408894
14	DE	0,1593	29	CZ	0,022932634
15	PT	0,15562			

Cash Flow of European Banking in 2021-Q4

	NSA	201609	201612	201703	201706	201709	201712	201803	201806	201809	201812	201903	201906	201909	201912	202003	202006	202009	202012	202103	202106	202109	202112																							
AT	☆	0,067	☆	0,089	☆	0,103	☆	0,111	☆	0,1	☆	0,094	☆	0,106	☆	0,091	☆	0,085	☆	0,092	☆	0,093	☆	0,087	☆	0,083	☆	0,085	☆	0,111	☆	0,134	☆	0,156	☆	0,177	☆	0,198	☆	0,2	☆	0,196	☆	0,18		
BE	☆	0,065	☆	0,065	☆	0,089	☆	0,111	☆	0,113	☆	0,081	☆	0,113	☆	0,118	☆	0,118	☆	0,061	☆	0,061	☆	0,093	☆	0,127	☆	0,143	☆	0,155	☆	0,196	☆	0,206	☆	0,203	☆	0,178								
BG	☆	0,191	☆	0,212	☆	0,215	☆	0,172	☆	0,186	☆	0,175	☆	0,146	☆	0,164	☆	0,15	☆	0,169	☆	0,165	☆	0,145	☆	0,144	☆	0,122	☆	0,16	☆	0,175	☆	0,183	☆	0,205	☆	0,177	☆	0,159	☆	0,166	☆	0,2		
CY	☆	0,182	☆	0,194	☆	0,188	☆	0,199	☆	0,215	☆	0,232	☆	0,205	☆	0,201	n.a.	n.a.	☆	0,229	☆	0,256	☆	0,252	☆	0,281	☆	0,246	☆	0,24	☆	0,243	☆	0,264	☆	0,291	☆	0,367	☆	0,369	☆	0,394				
CZ	☆	0,111	☆	0,113	☆	0,129	☆	0,184	☆	0,148	☆	0,102	☆	0,051	☆	0,047	☆	0,015	☆	0,034	☆	0,023	☆	0,029	☆	0,029	☆	0,026	☆	0,043	☆	0,026	☆	0,029	☆	0,022	☆	0,024	☆	0,022	☆	0,042	☆	0,023		
DE	☆	0,061	☆	0,081	☆	0,099	☆	0,112	☆	0,114	☆	0,117	☆	0,125	☆	0,126	☆	0,12	☆	0,112	☆	0,124	☆	0,113	☆	0,111	☆	0,1	☆	0,104	☆	0,139	☆	0,152	☆	0,138	☆	0,172	☆	0,184	☆	0,186	☆	0,159		
DK	☆	0,032	☆	0,046	☆	0,056	☆	0,064	☆	0,06	☆	0,066	☆	0,061	☆	0,045	☆	0,048	☆	0,024	☆	0,032	☆	0,036	☆	0,03	☆	0,03	☆	0,038	☆	0,047	☆	0,051	☆	0,071	☆	0,07	☆	0,072	☆	0,065	☆	0,069		
EE	☆	0,239	☆	0,235	☆	0,238	☆	0,216	☆	0,22	☆	0,223	☆	0,202	☆	0,213	☆	0,213	☆	0,223	☆	0,247	☆	0,194	☆	0,2	☆	0,211	☆	0,219	☆	0,225	☆	0,235	☆	0,253	☆	0,281	☆	0,259	☆	0,227	☆	0,236	☆	0,222
ES	☆	0,035	☆	0,048	☆	0,044	☆	0,05	☆	0,062	☆	0,07	☆	0,063	☆	0,065	☆	0,068	☆	0,074	☆	0,068	☆	0,064	☆	0,06	☆	0,065	☆	0,073	☆	0,094	☆	0,101	☆	0,102	☆	0,119	☆	0,125	☆	0,136	☆	0,142		
FI	☆	0,143	☆	0,113	☆	0,103	☆	0,094	☆	0,092	☆	0,122	☆	0,105	☆	0,123	☆	0,1	☆	0,094	☆	0,1	☆	0,087	☆	0,073	☆	0,087	☆	0,086	☆	0,108	☆	0,113	☆	0,093	☆	0,13	☆	0,128	☆	0,159	☆	0,127		
FR	☆	0,067	☆	0,073	☆	0,086	☆	0,089	☆	0,084	☆	0,086	☆	0,082	☆	0,079	☆	0,08	☆	0,077	☆	0,078	☆	0,077	☆	0,076	☆	0,083	☆	0,091	☆	0,118	☆	0,126	☆	0,128	☆	0,142	☆	0,148	☆	0,154	☆	0,149		
GR	☆	0,035	☆	0,033	☆	0,032	☆	0,032	☆	0,034	☆	0,035	☆	0,047	☆	0,048	☆	0,055	☆	0,061	☆	0,047	☆	0,054	☆	0,056	☆	0,071	☆	0,079	☆	0,096	☆	0,105	☆	0,126	☆	0,142	☆	0,159	☆	0,171	☆	0,194		
HR	☆	0,098	☆	0,109	☆	0,105	☆	0,113	☆	0,108	☆	0,134	☆	0,141	☆	0,131	☆	0,126	☆	0,143	☆	0,141	☆	0,141	☆	0,146	☆	0,149	☆	0,159	☆	0,162	☆	0,156	☆	0,182	☆	0,196	☆	0,199	☆	0,182	☆	0,212		
HU	☆	0,072	☆	0,089	☆	0,089	☆	0,082	☆	0,091	☆	0,095	☆	0,106	☆	0,097	☆	0,083	☆	0,105	☆	0,1	☆	0,094	☆	0,089	☆	0,102	☆	0,095	☆	0,095	☆	0,092	☆	0,098	☆	0,096	☆	0,093	☆	0,095	☆	0,087		
IE	☆	0,071	☆	0,097	☆	0,092	☆	0,089	☆	0,091	☆	0,101	☆	0,114	☆	0,11	☆	0,107	☆	0,107	☆	0,107	☆	0,108	☆	0,119	☆	0,118	☆	0,144	☆	0,141	☆	0,156	☆	0,183	☆	0,188	☆	0,223	☆	0,269	☆	0,278	☆	0,292
IS	☆	0	☆	0	☆	0	☆	0	☆	0	☆	0,114	☆	0,129	☆	0,129	☆	0,124	☆	0,109	☆	0,112	☆	0,104	☆	0,105	☆	0,101	☆	0,109	☆	0,096	☆	0,104	☆	0,075	☆	0,081	☆	0,093	☆	0,086	☆	0,081		
IT	☆	0,012	☆	0,013	☆	0,021	☆	0,028	☆	0,028	☆	0,037	☆	0,033	☆	0,044	☆	0,049	☆	0,049	☆	0,049	☆	0,051	☆	0,048	☆	0,049	☆	0,036	☆	0,052	☆	0,059	☆	0,076	☆	0,137	☆	0,148	☆	0,159	☆	0,165	☆	0,151
LT	☆	0,184	☆	0,213	☆	0,212	☆	0,206	☆	0,244	☆	0,245	☆	0,21	☆	0,206	☆	0,225	☆	0,247	☆	0,236	☆	0,231	☆	0,23	☆	0,281	☆	0,305	☆	0,339	☆	0,38	☆	0,368	☆	0,439	☆	0,41	☆	0,406	☆	0,425		
LU	☆	0,097	☆	0,091	☆	0,106	☆	0,138	☆	0,133	☆	0,119	☆	0,103	☆	0,124	☆	0,149	☆	0,163	☆	0,122	☆	0,147	☆	0,145	☆	0,144	☆	0,117	☆	0,16	☆	0,165	☆	0,166	☆	0,211	☆	0,212	☆	0,225	☆	0,238	☆	0,264
LV	☆	0,219	☆	0,211	☆	0,229	☆	0,238	☆	0,226	☆	0,242	☆	0,267	☆	0,266	☆	0,238	☆	0,265	☆	0,248	☆	0,218	☆	0,235	☆	0,258	☆	0,3	☆	0,28	☆	0,26	☆	0,301	☆	0,264	☆	0,291	☆	0,267	☆	0,363		
MT	☆	0,026	☆	0,03	☆	0,037	☆	0,039	☆	0,035	☆	0,044	☆	0,043	☆	0,034	☆	0,033	☆	0,036	☆	0,036	☆	0,197	☆	0,199	☆	0,221	☆	0,234	☆	0,219	☆	0,213	☆	0,219	☆	0,239	☆	0,233	☆	0,232	☆	0,252	☆	0,272
NL	☆	0,069	☆	0,066	☆	0,084	☆	0,063	☆	0,074	☆	0,064	☆	0,077	☆	0,072	☆	0,086	☆	0,08	☆	0,087	☆	0,078	☆	0,084	☆	0,073	☆	0,091	☆	0,121	☆	0,147	☆	0,133	☆	0,156	☆	0,153	☆	0,167	☆	0,144		
PL	☆	0,047	☆	0,044	☆	0,046	☆	0,048	☆	0,053	☆	0,05	☆	0,056	☆	0,045	☆	0,056	☆	0,056	☆	0,074	☆	0,05	☆	0,038	☆	0,042	☆	0,041	☆	0,045	☆	0,03	☆	0,019	☆	0,023	☆	0,031	☆	0,021	☆	0,023	☆	0,029
PT	☆	0,033	☆	0,03	☆	0,037	☆	0,037	☆	0,043	☆	0,055	☆	0,04	☆	0,057	☆	0,054	☆	0,056	☆	0,056	☆	0,052	☆	0,055	☆	0,051	☆	0,066	☆	0,064	☆	0,09	☆	0,081	☆	0,095	☆	0,112	☆	0,125	☆	0,142	☆	0,156
RO	☆	0,129	☆	0,15	☆	0,136	☆	0,133	☆	0,119	☆	0,159	☆	0,144	☆	0,137	☆	0,135	☆	0,145	☆	0,138	☆	0,145	☆	0,145	☆	0,144	☆	0,147	☆	0,16	☆	0,158	☆	0,148	☆	0,166	☆	0,139	☆	0,144	☆	0,141	☆	0,136
SE	☆	0,103	☆	0,067	☆	0,122	☆	0,122	☆	0,117	☆	0,082	☆	0,095	☆	0,104	☆	0,101	☆	0,088	☆	0,098	☆	0,078	☆	0,085	☆	0,08	☆	0,125	☆	0,134	☆	0,131	☆	0,11	☆	0,164	☆	0,162	☆	0,177	☆	0,114		
SI	☆	0,114	☆	0,119	☆	0,136	☆	0,119	☆	0,106	☆	0,112	☆	0,112	☆	0,106	☆	0,11	☆	0,122	☆	0,127	☆	0,119	☆	0,121	☆	0,158	☆	0,137	☆	0,191	☆	0,188	☆	0,204	☆	0,212	☆	0,229	☆	0,233	☆	0,236		
SK	☆	0,043	☆	0,055	☆	0,063	☆	0,067	☆	0,029	☆	0,06	☆	0,055	☆	0,031	☆	0,018	☆	0,047	☆	0,032	☆	0,044	☆	0,046	☆	0,053	☆	0,043	☆	0,052	☆	0,063	☆	0,079	☆	0,16	☆	0,173	☆	0,149	☆	0,143		